

МЕТОДЫ СОЗДАНИЯ И ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ГЕОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ОТРАСЛИ НА ОСНОВЕ РУССКОГО И АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКОВ

Кодирова Дилрабо Шамсидиновна

Навоийский государственный педагогический Институт

Аннотация:

В статье рассматриваются процессы становления английской терминологической системы в русской лексикологии геологической отрасли. Автор отмечает морфологические, лексико-семантические, заимствованные методы использования и создания новых геологических терминов на основе английского и русского языков.

***Ключевые слова:** морфологический метод, терминологическая система, заимствования, геологическая терминология, образование.*

METHODS OF CREATING AND USING A TERMINOLOGY SYSTEM OF THE GEOLOGICAL INDUSTRY BASED ON RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

Kodirova Dilrabo Shamsidinovna

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract:

The article examines the processes of formation of the English terminological system in the Russian lexicology of the geological branch. The author notes morphological, lexical-semantic, borrowed methods of using and creating new geological terms based on English and Russian languages.

***Key words:** morphological method, terminological system, borrowings, geological terminology, formation.*

The formation of the terminological base in its usual understanding in English began in the XVIII century, in connection with the development of geology. At that time, geology was being formed as a full-fledged scientific discipline, which was the impetus for the creation of a specialized system of terms.[1, p. 7]

English terminology in geological science was formed for the most part by borrowing words from the German language, since the first works on mining began to appear in Germany. Borrowings from the terminology of the German language can be observe on the following examples *stulm* – *штольня*, *miningsurveyor* - *маршнейдер*, *wornauger* - *шнейг*, *zinc* - *цинк*, *soil* - *грунт*. The term *molybdenum* - *молибден*, was borrowed from the Latin language – *molybdenum*

The English geological term system is characterized by proximity to the commonly used vocabulary. This feature is closely related to the functional variability of the term, which moves in two directions: differentiation and integration, is reflected in the pragmatic mobility of terminological units that migrate from common vocabulary to special terminology and vice versa.

The process of transition of a commonly used word into the category of terms can be traced by the example of the term *reeler* – *to reel* - *крутиться, вертеться*, in mining terminology this term will have the meaning – *намоточная машина*. The semantic processes of English geological terminology are based on three directions: reduction of components of meaning; increase of components and substitution (replacement of some components with others). On the way of reducing the components of the denotative value, you can see the process of its expansion, and on the way of increasing components, respectively, the process of narrowing. [2, p. 256]

For example: *to doctor* in the field of mining is described as *to dress the maggy heads* (*обрабатывать руду низкого качества*), coming from *oredressing treatment* (*процесс обогащения руды*). Also, borrowing words from other term systems or common vocabulary plays a significant role in understanding the concept of the term. In most cases, borrowings follow the principle of adjacency of the designated concepts, for example: *gallery* - *галерея*, in mining - an underground gallery, that is, a tunnel for collecting materials.

Thus, it can be traced that the formation of a word as a term takes place in several stages: the creation of a term, for example, by borrowing from another term system or from common vocabulary, the expansion or narrowing of its semantics in connection with the rapidly developing progress in the field of mining. Morphological method – a combination of morphemes based on available in the language of the basics, is the most common in term formation. In this method, the combination of morphemes can be performed by: prefixing, that is, adding a prefix to the generating base, for example: *afterinjection* – *подпрыск*, *cross-drift* – *диагональный штрек*, *misconvergence* - *нарушение сходимости*, *noncutting* – *холостой ход*, *unslaked* - *негашиённый*, *aftercooler* - *доохладитель*, *afterquenching* – *дополнительное тушение*; suffixation, that is, by adding a suffix to the base: *tractor* - *трактор*, *bulldozer* –

бульдозер, clipper – отсекаТЕЛЬ, dynamite- динамит, vulcanite- вулканизированная резина, dedrite - дендрит, moistureless – не содержащий влаги, breakage- поломка; the word structure, i.e. a new term, is formed by combining already existing bases, for example: cathod-follower – катодный повторитель, signal - noise – сигнал-шум, brake-gear – тормозная система, radiospectroscopy – радиоспектроскопия, carbon-bond – углеродная связь, antifreeze - антифриз, coalhole – подвал для хранения угля.

The noted morphological features of a scientific and technical style as well as English geological terminology have a positive, direct impact on the communicative nature, on the accuracy of conveying information to the reader or scientist working in this field. Morphology is an integral part of geological terminology and has a huge impact on the accuracy of the transmission of meaning and its understanding. It is in the field of morphology that lexical units and ways of their formation are studied by prefixation, affixation, word composition and derivation. Also, from the point of view of morphology, as a section of grammar, grammatical constructions of sentences, nominal constructions, the use of prepositional-nominal combinations instead of adverbs, the omission of articles, the consistency and consistency of the presentation of the material, as well as the rules for constructing a scientific and technical text as a whole are determined.

The morphological way of creating new terms is, word production. The morphological method is understood as the creation of new words by adding word-building affixes to existing stems. With the help of this method, new lexical units are formed, which is why modern linguists consider this method of term formation to be one of the most productive. The need for a morphological way of forming terms is caused by the need to name new concepts, objects, techniques, and so on, due to the rapid developing technologies from the field of science and production.

Modern processes of formation of new terms in the terminological system of the mining sphere increase the requirements for the functioning of these terms. Their main purpose is to enable communication between specialists in the mining industry. For the development of science and technology, the processes of interethnic and international cooperation are a characteristic feature, which inevitably affects the trends in terminological names. All this leads to the use of international means of term formation, as well as to the direct borrowing of terminological names.

The formation of new terms as a result of the disintegration of a word into homonyms, that is, the acquisition of new meanings by the same lexical unit, is called the lexico-semantic method of term formation. Over time, the various meanings of a polysemantic term may lose their semantic connection with each other and turn into independent words, that is, homonyms.

Affixation - the formation of new terms by joining them the basis of certain word-building affixes. The most productive ways of affixing are prefixing and suffix. The morphological way of forming the terms of the English geological term system, such as prefixation, can be seen in the following examples: *underconsumption* – *недостаточное потребление*, *undergroundcoal* – *уголь, добытый подземным способом*. Terms formed with the prefix *under-* basically indicate a position under something, subordination, insignificant importance. The formation of terms using the prefixes *dis-*, *mis-*, *un-* and *sub-* can be seen in these examples: *acidity coefficient* – *коэффициент кислотности шахтных вод*; *coexistence* - *совместимость*; *unknown mineral* – *неизвестный материал*; *disbond* – *нарушение связности*, *misconvergence* – *нарушение сходимости*; *subsection* – *подсекция*. Examples of terms with the prefix *non-* can be seen in the data examples: *non reinforced concrete* – *безжелезобетона*; *non ferrous* – *цветные металлы*.

The after prefix has the meanings «next», «back», «going after». Examples of word formation of English terms mining topics can be seen in the following examples: *aftertreatment technology* – *последующая переработка*; *afterdamp* – *газ после взрыва рудничного газа*; *afterquenching* – *дополнительное тушение*. The examples below show the formation of English mining terms with the prefix *by-*: *byproduct* – *побочный продукт*; *bylaw* – *правила внутреннего распорядка*. Examples of terms with the prefix *cross-*: *cross-drift* – *диагональный штрек*, *crossbedding* – *диагональная слоистость*, *crossband* – *поперечный срез*, *crosssectionarea* – *площадь поперечного сечения*.

Terms are formed by suffixation by adding various suffixes to their base. The most productive suffix, is *-er*, with the help of which terms are formed denoting persons by type of activity, as well as the names of technical means. For example: *miner* - *горняк*; *worker* - *рабочий*; *clarifier* – *очистительная установка*.

The suffix *-age* appeared in modern English due to borrowing from Latin. In English, this suffix is most often added to the verb, and with its help word formation of nouns with different meanings takes place. In the terminology of mining industry, with the help of this suffix, the following terms were formed: *haulagesystem* - *система транспортировки угля*; *spillage* - *просыпание (ископаемого при загрузке на конвейер, в вагонетки)*; *passage* – *туннель*, *breakage* - *вторичное дробление*, *acreage* - *нефтяная площадь в акрах*; and many others.

Terms with *-ite* suffixes are found in scientific language to refer to nouns denoting various types of minerals, fossils, explosives, chemical products: *monazite* - *манацит*; *apatite* - *апатит*; *magnetite* - *магнетит*; *titanite* - *титанит*; *dendrite* - *дендрит*; *roburite* – *робурит*.

Another morphological way of forming terms in English geological terminology is compounding. With this method, new terms are created by adding two or more words into one. Such words can be written both together and with a hyphen. The following terms can serve as examples of this method of forming terms in the English terminology system: *timeline* - *расписание стыковки*, *micrometer* - *scale* - *шкала микрометра*, *carryback* - *сползание материала*; *workgroup* - *рабочая группа*, *fuel-cell-powered mining equipment* - *горное оборудование на топливных элементах*, *coal handling facility* - *механизмы топливоподачи*.

Another way to form the terms of the English term system is conversion, that is, the transition of a word from one part of speech to another. The morphological paradigm acts as a word-forming means during conversion, namely, the ability of the paradigm and its constituent endings to convey the meaning of a certain part of speech. The use of a term in a new syntactic function is accompanied not only by its application in the desired syntactic position, but also the acquisition of a new morphological indicator by the term. That is why conversion is often referred to as morphological and syntactic methods of forming lexical units. The conversion can be seen in the following examples: *sampling* – *as a noun* - *образец*, in mining terminology turns into a verb – *собирать пробы*, *healthhazard* - *adjective* «*вредный для здоровья*», in mining it can turn into a noun «*вредные условия производства*»; the verb *to mine* - *добывать*, turns into a noun - *mining* – *добыча*; *to extract* – *добывать руду*, turns into a noun *extraction* – *выемка руды*.

Another lexico-semantic way of forming terms English mining terminology is a borrowing. Terms can be borrowed from other English terminology, with common vocabulary, as well as from other languages. Quantitative the composition of English mining terminology is equal to the amount of knowledge on each historical stage of mining development. The most frequent borrowings are from common vocabulary. So, for example, the words: *room* - *комната*, in the English mining terminology – *очистная выработка*; *pillar* - *столб*, *стержень* – *камерная выемка*; *bed* - *кроватка*, in mining – *пласт*, *почва*; the word *pit* - *яма*, moved from common vocabulary to terminology mining with the meaning – *development*; the word *roof* - *крыша*, in English mining terminology will mean *a hanging side or an upper or arched fold wing*.

The described methods of term formation by borrowing words and terms from common vocabulary, other languages or term systems, the creation homonyms, reveal the lexical and semantic features of the functioning of English terms in geological terminology. Based on the descriptions of these methods and examples, it is possible to accurately trace the changes in the term system, which gives reason to consider the English geological term system as a living and constantly evolving process.

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